

Human Resources Management Strategy for Improving Performance at PT XYZ

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Abstract:- Employee performance influences company performance. Performance management supports the overall goals of the organization not only on the performance of each individual but also on the performance of the organization. Maintaining optimal performance is a challenge because during pandemic there was a decline in employee performance. So in this study the authors have a goal to know the factors that cause lower performance and know the strategies that can be done to improve performance. The method used a qualitative method, with the SWOT method and then processing the data using AHP method. The results of the study show that three factors have the greatest weight, namely employees with higher education, harmonious work environment, and massive access to information and training. The objective factor that has the greatest weight is strength. The strategy that gets the most weight is employee who are included in the talent pool category according their respective jobs, and employees who have been trained will become trainer in their respective department.

Keywords:- AHP, Performance, Strategy, SWOT.

I. INTRODUCTION

The ability of a company to manage its workforce effectively can have a positive influence on company performance. This is due to the influence of employee performance on company performance, where the use of high performance practices can have positive impact on company financial performance through increased employee commitment, low turnover rates, reduces recruitment costs, increased productivity and provides high attractiveness to the workforce. According to Costello in Setyawan (2018) performance management supports the overall goals of the organization by linking the work of each worker and manager to the overall mission of the work unit. This is caused by several factors such as the existence of large-scale social restrictions that make the work of employees in the organization less effective, the existence of a work from home (WFH) system which results in reduced or intensive wages, and the occurrence of large-scale job terminations. This challenge is also experienced by PT XYZ which is a company engaged in services. One of the biggest parts in PT XYZ is the operational division. Based on the results of the annual employee performance appraisal at PT XYZ, there are still challenges in maintaining optimal performance. This can

be seen from the results of employee performance appraisal over the last three years as follows:

Table I: Annual Employee Performance Assessment

Category	Year		
	2018	2019	2020
Very Good	7,6%	2,0%	1,3%
Good	22,0%	21,0%	12,0%
Enough	61,0%	60,0%	80,0%
Less Good	9,4%	17,0%	6,7%
Not Good	0%	0%	0%

Employee performance acts as a function of ability and motivation. A person's ability is closely related to the competence he has (Widaningsih, Sukristanta, and Kasno, 2020). This is evidenced by Rande (2016), where competence has a very strong relationship with employee performance. Competence is a set of skills, knowledge and individual behavior in carrying out their work properly (Awasthidan Kumar, 2016). Competence describes the standards that a person must possess to carry out a position in detail such as the characteristics, knowledge and skills required to enable them to carry out their duties and responsibilities effectively and to be able to achieve work professional quality standards covering many aspects. The competency gap is a discrepancy between the competencies desired by the company and what employees actually have. Based on the results of a pre-survey conducted through interviews with PT XYZ's operational managers, competency gaps were still found. This can be seen from the three competency categories as follows: First, there is a gap in functional ability, in terms of employees who do work not in accordance with their job description. Second, the high gap in managerial ability is characterized by the process of making work plans that are still not in line with company targets and goals, low initiative in conducting evaluations, and a gap in leadership ability. Third, discrepancies were found in human attributes, which in this case occurred in communication skills that were not yet effective so that there was often misinformation, as well as a lack of collaboration skills. To overcome this competency gap, a strategy is needed that is able to develop skills and help employees to adjust their abilities as desired by the company. The competencies required by companies for certain types of work are also influenced by various factors (Shivanjali, et al, 2019). Based on the results of a pre-survey conducted using the unstructured interview method with operational managers of PT XYZ, the factors that influence employee competency gaps are individual internal factors and individual external factors. The

most influencing internal factors are intellectual ability and work experience. Meanwhile, the external factors that influence are co-worker support and company support. The results of the pre-survey show that most (47%) employees have experience of more than 5 years, and only 15.5% have experience of less than one year. Length of work has an influence on employee competence, because experience also influences employee mastery in carrying out their duties and work. Research conducted by Muntazeri and Indrayanto (2018), and Ochonma et al (2018) shows that a person's work experience affects performance, but different results are shown by Devita (2017) where the work experience factor has little effect on a person's performance. Based on organizational challenges in maintaining optimal performance and the influence of internal factors which include intellectual abilities and experience as well as external factors which include co-workers and organizational support, the authors will conduct research on HR management strategies in improving performance at PT XYZ.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Performance

Performance is the result achieved by workers or employees in quality or quantity in accordance with their duties and responsibilities. Performance is the level of achievement of results on the implementation of certain tasks. Company performance is the level of achievement of results in order to realize company goals (Mulyadi in Djamil and Zaenuddin, 2018). According to Afandi (2018) Performance is the result of work that can be achieved by a person or group of people in a company in accordance with their respective authorities and responsibilities in an effort to achieve organizational goals legally, does not violate the law and does not conflict with morals and ethics. Competence is a combination of knowledge, skills, attitudes, and personal characteristics needed to achieve success in a job. Competence is learnable, measured by agreed standards, developed through training. (Marwansyah, 2016). The definition of competence according to Chouchan and Srivastava (2014) is a series of success factors needed to achieve the desired results in specific job positions and roles within an organization. These success factors are a combination of knowledge, skills and abilities that are specifically explained in terms of their position and role at work. In addition, competence also covers a series of behaviors that help in achieving the desired results. Competence is conceptualized as something that a person can do and can be observed. The theory of Human Capital states that experience is an employee's investment in himself, which will increase abilities, and have an impact on performance. An employee's performance will continue to change due to the accumulation of work experience. This is due to the accumulation of knowledge, skills, work skills, and abilities that will improve performance (Ochonma, et al., 2018). Coworker support is related to employee trust in the willingness of coworkers to help do their job. The concept of co-worker competence is a key factor that influences the way employees perceive their co-workers, this is able to drive individual or organizational success. A person's behavior and views can be influenced by a person's assessment of the support of his colleagues. The existence of positive employee perceptions of co-workers can indirectly improve contextual

performance through increased work engagement (Tringale, 2018). Competency management is a form of human resource management that links company strategic policies with human resource development and organizational behavior so that they are able to achieve better results and play a role in helping achieve organizational goals. Competency management supports the integration between human resource planning and the organization's business planning through a competency gap assessment process which is carried out by assessing the capacity of human resources based on the actual competencies they currently have compared to the capacity needed to be able to achieve the vision, mission and business objectives of the organization.

III. RESEARCH AND METHOD

Mixed research methods in this study were applied to address issues related to HR management strategies in improving performance at PT XYZ. Quantitative data will be used to find the influence of variables and the best strategy in managing human resources at PT XYZ. A qualitative approach will be used to formulate alternative strategies for HR management. The population in this study is the operational staff of PT XYZ. Meanwhile, the sample is part of the population that has the same characteristics as the population. According to Arikunto (2012) if the subject is less than 100 then it is not necessary to use a sample but what is used is the population. This study did not use a sample but used a population because the number of PT XYZ operational staff totaled 60 people. working more than 5 years. The selection of respondents was carried out based on positions capable of determining policy (Helingo et al, 2017). Data analysis used in this research is SWOT analysis (strength, weakness, opportunity, threats) and AHP (Analytical Hierarchy Process). The SWOT-AHP method is a combination of the two methods. In the SWOT-AHP analysis process, pairwise comparisons are performed in the SWOT analysis. In the structure of the SWOT-AHP method, the strategic factors resulting from the SWOT analysis will be used to determine the right strategy quantitatively for the AHP method (Lee, et al., 2021). The SWOT analysis method can be considered the most basic analytical method but has great benefit to see a topic or problem from 4 (four) different sides. The results of the SWOT analysis are in the form of directions or recommendations to maintain strengths and to increase profits in terms of existing opportunities and reduce deficiencies and avoid threats. AHP is a decision support model that will break down complex multi-factor or multi-criteria problems into a hierarchy. Hierarchy is defined as representing a complex problem in a multi-level structure where the first level is the goal, followed by the level of factors, criteria, sub criteria, and so on down to the last level of alternatives.

IV. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Based on the results of interviews conducted with experts at PT XYZ stated that "PT XYZ employees have good skills in analyzing problems with systematic and sequential solutions. PT XYZ employees are accustomed to solving problems by breaking down complex problems into smaller points so that they are easier to solve. This result is supported

by Yordanova (2018) which states that thinking. Analytical is an important component in one's intellectual ability that allows one to solve problems effectively and efficiently. This ability occurs using a methodical approach that makes complex problems into smaller pieces that are simpler and easier to study. Employees who have work experience have competencies appropriate to the work being done. This can increase employee motivation at work and obtain high performance. In addition, employees will also work faster and do not need to adapt to the tasks being carried out due to experience. Employees who have higher work experience will be better able to adjust their behavior to achieve higher performance compared to employees who are inexperienced (Gabler, 2018). The strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats that have been described are then included in the Internal Factors Analysis Summary (IFAS)-External Factors Analysis Summary (EFAS) matrix of employee performance as follows:

Table II: IFAS Matrix Employee

Category	Strength
S1	Employees have higher education
S2	Employees have good analytical thinking skills
S3	Employees have work experience in the same field
	Weakness
W1	Employee communication skills are not good
W2	Low productivity figures
W3	Lack of appreciation from the company for success employee

Table III: EFAS Matrix Employee

Category	Opportunity
O1	Harmonious work environment
O2	Access to massive external information and training
O3	Availability of external training on digitization and mechanization
	Threats
T1	Decrease in product sales during the pandemic
T2	The number of competitors with similar fields

Table II: IFAS Matrix Employee

Criteria	Sub-Criteria
Strength	Employee with higher education
	Good Analytical thinking skill
	Employee have work experience
Weakness	Employee communication skills are not good
	Low productivity
	Lack of company appreciation for employee
Opportunity	Harmonious work environment
	Access to information and massive training
	Availability of external digitalization training and mechanization
Threats	Decrease product sales during pandemic

	The number of competitors with similar field
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The results from AHP are follows:

Table IV: Criteria Matrix with Eigen Vector

	S	W	O	T	Total	Eigen
S	0,49	0,47	0,52	0,42	1,90	0,48
W	0,16	0,16	0,13	0,25	0,70	0,18
O	0,25	0,32	0,26	0,25	1,07	0,27
T	0,10	0,05	0,09	0,08	0,32	0,08
Σ	1,00	1,00	1,00	1,00	4,00	1,00

Table V: Final Calculation

Criteria	S-O	W-O	S-T	WT
Strength	1,23	0,53	1,06	0,53
	0,07	0,04	0,09	0,03
	0,31	0,16	0,26	0,16
Weakness	0,18	0,37	0,18	0,37
	0,03	0,06	0,03	0,06
	0,07	0,11	0,07	0,11
Opportunity	0,71	0,51	0,31	0,31
	0,40	0,34	0,13	0,20
	0,06	0,05	0,03	0,03
Threats	0,06	0,06	0,12	0,12
	0,09	0,09	0,18	0,15
Total	5,57	4,14	0,18	0,15

V. CONCLUSION

The conclusions from the results of this study are as follows: Intellectual ability factors affect employee performance. The indicator that gets the highest weight is the employee's high level of education. The experience factor influences employee performance, in this study the indicator that gets the highest weight is employees who have work experience in the same field. Co-worker factors affect employee performance, in this study the indicator that gets the highest weight is a harmonious work environment. Organizational support factors influence employee performance, in this study the indicators that get the highest weight are access to information and massive external training. The strategy that gets the most weight is Strength-opportunity, namely: Implementing an internal talent pool program by identifying employees who have good performance and are able to be developed. Providing development programs for employees who are included in the talent pool to be able to access external information and training in accordance with their respective work fields with financing from the company. Employees who have conducted external training are then made trainers in their respective departments.

Based on the conclusions above and with the hope that research can present better research results, the authors try to provide some input as follows: XYZ Company can select employees who have good performance to be identified and given more specific programs. XYZ Company can improve employee training programs to increase employee productivity

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